

Sieve for Mersenne prime numbers

author Alessandro Boatto 19 Febbraio 2019 , Italy , Jesolo(VE)

Abstract :

The algorithm generates many odd numbers, but only prime numbers of mersenne and not common prime numbers.

$$M_{p(n=0)} = \frac{2^{\frac{n+2}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5$$

The consequence is :

$$M_{p(n=0)} = \frac{2^{\frac{n+2}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5 = 2^p - 1$$

Example

$$M_2 = \frac{2^{\frac{6}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5 = 2^2 - 1$$

$$M_3 = \frac{2^{\frac{8}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5 = 2^3 - 1$$

$$M_5 = \frac{2^{\frac{12}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5 = 2^5 - 1$$

$$M_7 = \frac{2^{\frac{16}{2}} - 1}{2} - 0, 5 = 2^7 - 1$$

References

- [1] Davenport,H. (2008). *The Higher Arithmetic: An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*. Cambridge University Press.